

Supplementary Information:

CpG Methylation Protects DNA Against Ionizing Radiation

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Radiation Damage to DNA Origami Nanoframes

Figure S1: Percentage of intact frames left after exposure to various absorbed doses of electrons (black squares) and carbon ions (red circles).

Relative OH Radical Yields

Figure S2: UV absorbance at 268 nm of DNA origami solutions in tris-containing buffer ([tris] = 10 mM) vs. absorbed dose after irradiation with electrons (black squares) and carbon ions (red circles) and the approximate linear fits to estimate the average radical yield ratio between the two irradiation conditions. Lower dose rate electron irradiation was also tested (blue triangles) which resulted in a non-linear profile of tris-OH yields vs. dose suggesting that the rate of OH radical generation is slower than the rate of OH recombination. The former two conditions were therefore adapted for the DNA irradiation experiments to have comparable conditions between electron and carbon ion irradiation, respectively.

AGE Analysis of Denatured Samples

Figure S3: AGE analysis of denatured samples. Raw gel image (A) of lanes loaded with controls, electron-, and carbon ion-irradiated samples. The extracted profiles of the lanes are shown in B with gaussian fits corresponding to the various bands associated to the components of the denatured sample. The dose dependent evolution of the estimated band intensity containing both the methylated and unmethylated strands is plotted in C while D shows the relative mobility of the DNA origami scaffold/scaffold fragments approximated from the 1 kb ladder mass steps.